

IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880406>

Abstract. *This article presents factors affecting the potential and level of human resources in the preschool education system, advanced foreign experiences of human resources management, and methods of using them in preschool education organizations of our republic.*

Keywords: *management, authoritarian style, bureaucratic style, authoritarian leader, democratic style, liberal style, modern leader.*

INTRODUCTION

The management process is determined on the one hand by the goals, instructions and abilities of the manager, and on the other hand by the situation in which management is carried out. Determining factors of the situation arise from the nature of the issue, the potential for solving employee problems and the prevailing conditions of the external environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Management style refers to a manager's typical behavior and ways of behaving.

According to the participation of managers in the decisions made, the ideal-typical authoritarian, relational and autonomous styles of management are distinguished.

The authoritarian style of management is distinguished by the manifestation of individuality and centralization of will when there is power for the manager. The manager decides and orders, the employees must follow these orders. Different situations are evident in this:

- commanding style. The manager decides and gives strict orders without the participation of the managed, and the employees are obliged to follow him under the risk of punishment;
- autocratic style. In this the manager has a large apparatus for power at his disposal;
- bureaucratic style. The authority of the manager here derives from formal class arrangements. Managers and employees are subject to one detailed set of rules ;
- patriarchal (matriarchal) style. The manager, with the help of the "head of the family" role, cares and assumes all responsibility, explains and orders the decision, the employees obey him based on their unlimited trust ;
- courtesy style. The manager decides on his promotion based on the best unique qualities of the person and accordingly achieves a high personal status, the employees follow his decisions because they believe in his inner positive qualities.

The communication style of the CEO is characterized by the participation of employees in the decision-making process. In this case, it is important to distinguish between cases in house q :

- communication style. The manager finds it difficult to say that his decision has been made, and therefore makes a decision only after informing the employees, the employees can ask questions, express their opinion, but they must follow the orders ;
- matter h at style. The manager makes decisions only after detailed information and

discussion, and also takes into account suggestions made by employees about the decision and optimal solutions to the problem. Employees participate in discussions and implement the decisions made;

- Joint decision - making method. In this case, the manager identifies the problem and sets limited conditions for solving it, the employees make independent decisions about the activities carried out within the agreed limits, the manager allows, but reserves the right to protest. takes;

- autonomous style. The manager assumes the role of a moderator (i.e., aloof) in the decision-making process and struggles to consolidate solutions, while employees usually make decisions by majority when independent boundaries are not set.

of administrative behavior can be conditionally distinguished:

- autocratic: leader - executor;
- bureaucratic: management "wheel of nomenclature" - executor;
- democratic: leader — management "social wheel" — executor;
- aristocratic: leader - work incentive system - executor.

According to the analysis of scientific literature on management, leadership is divided into three types. These are authoritarian, democratic and free (liberal).

RESULTS

An authoritarian leader makes decisions alone and strictly determines the behavior of subordinates without giving them the opportunity to take initiative. Such a leader is characterized by a high assessment of his personality and insufficient assessment of the work and human qualities of his subordinates. He usually equates himself and the organization he manages, himself and the team subordinate to him, often "burns out" at work, he cannot imagine himself, forgets his personal life, works tirelessly, but does not care about subordinates. An authoritarian leader will often spare no efforts, including people, to achieve production goals. With such a leader, people feel like they are in a "volcano", in an emergency situation. They annoy them unnecessarily, get on their nerves, overuse them. This type can be included in the guide "How not to behave as a leader". However, an autocrat should not be confused with a strict leader.

The democratic style of leadership is to give subordinates the independence that corresponds to their qualifications and work characteristics, to solve work issues with their direct participation or at least after discussion with them, to create the necessary conditions for their work, to evaluate their actions objectively, to treat people positively and consider their needs. Such actions of the leader not only lead to anarchy by ruining the principles of monogamy, but also strengthen the leader's real authority and reputation, and help to create productive working conditions in the team. In this style of leadership, it is necessary to be aware of the concerns and interesting work of subordinates. One of the large Japanese companies has a rule: "Hour in a week, day in a month." It is precisely with such periodicity that the administration, including the top management, comes to the shop and works side by side with the employees on the conveyor. According to the initiators of this practice, it allows to maintain contact with employees, to know their mood, working and living conditions. This style of leadership is considered the best.

Liberal style. This is seen by many as ineffective when left to their own devices. But in some small teams, where superficial coercion and direction of activity are required, it is very important, such a style aims to be polite with employees, minimally interfere with their work process, respect the opinion of subordinates, encourage discussions about work, and so on.

Table 2 below compares leadership styles based on certain indicators.

Table 1.

Comparative analysis of leadership styles.

K indicators	Leadership styles		
	Autocratic	Democratic	Liberal
Decision making method	He will solve the problem by himself	making a decision, they first consult with their subordinates	yuq ori ra h barni waits for instructions or board waits for the decision
The method of communicating the decision to the executors	shows commands, commands	t offers , please	He begs , begs
Responsibility distribution	on his own takes or hand under - to loads	distributes responsibility according to rights	from himself removes responsibility _ _ _
To the initiative relationship	suppresses full initiative	r encourages and works for the benefit	use t ashabbus _ to those below submits
Staff to choose relationship	M a l aka is afraid of staff , looking for a way to be free from them .	He selects knowledgeable and skilled employees	with a selection of k addresses engage - don't
Attitudes towards lack of personal knowledge	thinks that everyone knows and can do things	constantly improves his skills, looks positively at recognition	fills up his knowledge , he advises others
Communication style _ _ _	o rali q saves, to circulation does not enter	d is in stepmother relationship treatment likes	from alo q a q afraid _ _ _ head q a - s initiative dealing with q _
Relationship with descriptive subordinates	Arabic for good health	A straight moral always controls itself _ _	formality requires discipline
To discipline relationship	He is a supporter of formalism and discipline	advocate meaningful discipline, treat people accordingly	x acts like this
The attitude of having a moral	considers punishment as the main method of	always uses different incentives	x acts like this

influence subordinates _ _ _	on education. Rewards some selected employees on holidays		
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DISCUSSION

A modern leader working in the preschool education system should, first of all, have a good understanding of the strategy, direction, goals and prospects of the organization he is leading. The leader should also know the personnel policy, where and what level of specialist is needed, and have clear and thorough knowledge of the fields .

A modern leader should have the following knowledge and skills :

1. Educational organization goals and tasks ;
2. and training activities of the preschool educational organization (if possible) ;
3. Ability to find and place personnel , solve issues of employment ;
4. Work to introduce innovations into the educational process ;
5. Always have information about your competitors ;
6. Apply punishment and incentive measures in a timely and fair manner ;
7. To be able to establish order and control in the organization and learn ways to establish control (to know);
8. He should always have good relations with employees and always increase their initiative in work , encourage them , support them and strive to increase the maximum educational efficiency as possible ;
9. The leader must always prevent conflicts, fully understand their causes and develop measures to prevent recurrence ;
10. making a decision, the leader must know and calculate their effect, result, profit and loss before making each decision ;
11. guide, move, apply to achieve greater success ;
12. It is necessary to inform all employees about each failure , to warn, clearly indicate the reasons for this failure, to use punishment, fine and similar measures, and to work out strict measures to prevent the failure from happening again ;
13. The leader should have accurate and thorough information about the education situation, policy, legislation and external partners of the country and analyze them (impact, result);
14. sciences that belong to the philosophical sciences (philosophy, ethics, aesthetics, logic)
15. should have social qualities , that is, he should use some employees who need help working under the leader . It is necessary to allocate funds for them ;
16. A leader should be able to attract and attract everyone to apply his opinion, as well as in terms of his appearance and his character .

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion , a modern leader , along with scientific knowledge and skills, must have mastered the art of self-care, as a person, he understands human values , traditions , and the goals and intentions of the people around him . It is important to understand and respect . Also, it is extremely important to properly organize the work of senior staff in the management of the organization. They should have sufficient knowledge of management methods, management tactics and strategies, and the tools used in them in order to effectively manage human resources.

There are authoritarian, relational, and autonomous styles of management, and leaders need to be able to use them effectively in different situations. Depending on what styles leaders pay more attention to, they can be divided into authoritarian, democratic and liberal leaders.

REFERENCES

1. I. U.Murakayev, I.S. Saidnazarov Fundamentals of Management. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2001.
2. J. Jalolov, I. Ahmedov. Marketing studies. -T.: 2005.
3. N.A.Volgina Ekonomika truda: rynochnye i sotsialnye aspekti: uchebno-metodicheskiy kompleks dlya podgotovki magistrrov. /Pod obshch. ed. NAVolgina.- M.: Izd-vo RAGS, 2010.
4. R.A. Fathitdinov. Strategic marketing. "Peter" - M .: 2006 g.
5. F.R. Valiyeva. "Management of preschool education". Study guide. - Tashkent: Fan Ziya publishing house. 2022
6. F.R. Valieva Ensuring continuity in the training of future professionals in the educational system.// European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences/ Volume 7 Number 6, 2019. ISSN 2056-5852
7. F.R. Valieva, Sh. Kurbanov Continuity in the education system // Wschodnioeuropejskie // East European science journal 12(52) 2019 45-52. 2020
8. F.R. Valieva To Develop Professional Training of Professionals Education Specialists by Ensuring //Print //International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD) Special Issue on International Research Development and Scientific Excellence in Academic Life Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 6470 2021